

Sampling

- The sample size administered for the study is 210 respondents. The sample size selected is in the ratio 1:5. The data were collected using google forms through a structured questionnaire.
- The nature of the study: The research study was exploratory in nature.

Limitations of the Study

- Individual difference in the people's perception was a limitation.
- Understanding detrimental stereotypes and conceptions about women and gender equality in corporates was a challenge.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Descriptive statistics is used to break down this information. Descriptive Statistics includes analysing data using frequency distribution, charts like bar graph etc. based on the user's requirement. In the data analysis section, we have illustrated using certain variables from the questionnaire.

Table 1: Reliability Statistics

Reliability Statistics			
Dimension	Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
Acceptance	.877	.900	
Skill set	.899		7
Social cultural barriers	.863		6
Competitiveness	.897		9
Work life balance	.898		7

Do you Think Women Marketers Seek Out Challenging Opportunities That Test Her Skills and Abilities?

Table 2: Relationship between Various Variables

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	42	20.0
Disagree	41	19.5
Neither agree nor disagree	42	20.0
Agree	60	28.6
Strongly Agree	25	11.9
Total	210	100.0

Table 2 Women marketers test her skills and abilities

Inference: Around 60% of them agree that women marketers seek for the challenging opportunities that test their skills and abilities, and around 40% of them disagreed. Thus, the majority of them agreed that most of the women marketers seek out challenging opportunities that tests their skills and abilities.

Do the Women Marketers Foresee the Future Trends that Will Influence the Company's Work?

Table 3: Women Marketers Foresee the Future Trends

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	28	13.3
Disagree	42	20.0
Neither agree nor disagree	48	22.9
Agree	57	27.1
Strongly Agree	35	16.7
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 60% of them agree that women marketers foresee the future trends that will influence the company's work, around 30% of them disagreed that women marketers foresee the future trends that will influence the company's work. Thus, the majority of them agreed that women marketers foresee the future trends that will influence the company's work.

Do Women Marketers Developed Cooperative Relationship among Their Co-Workers?

Table 4: Women Marketers Developed Cooperative Relationship among Her Co-Workers

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	30	14.3
Disagree	39	18.6
Neither agree nor disagree	46	21.9
Agree	51	24.3
Strongly Agree	44	21.0
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 50% of them agree that the women marketers developed a cooperative relationship among their co-workers and around 30% of them disagreed that the women marketers developed cooperative relationship among their co-workers. Thus, the most of them agreed that women marketers developed cooperative relationship among their co-workers.

Do You Think Women Marketers Help People to Progress in their Job by Learning New Skills?

Table 5: Women Marketers Help People to Progress in their Job by Learning News Kills

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	20	9.5
Disagree	46	21.9
Neither agree nor disagree	37	17.6
Agree	59	28.1
Strongly Agree	48	22.9
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 60% of them agree that women marketers help people to progress in their job by learning new skills and around 20% of them disagreed that women marketers help people to progress in their job by learning new skills and around 40% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers help people to progress in their job by learning new skills. We can conclude that the most of the population agreed that women marketers help people to progress in their job

by learning new skills.

Do You Think Women Marketers Follow the Promises and Commitments they Make?

Table 6: Women Marketers Follow the Promises and Commitments they Make

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	24	11.4
Disagree	42	20.0
Neither agree nor disagree	49	23.3
Agree	59	28.1
Strongly Agree	36	17.1
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 60% of them agree that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make. around 25% of them disagreed that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make and around 50% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make. We can conclude that the most of the population agreed women marketers follow through the promises and commitments they make.

Do You Think Women Marketers are Treated with Same Respect and Dignity as Men?

Table 7: Women Marketers are Treated with Same Respect and Dignity as Men

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	31	14.8
Disagree	63	30.0
Neither agree nor disagree	52	24.8
Agree	37	17.6
Strongly Agree	27	12.9
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 40% of them agree that women marketers are treated with same respect and dignity as men, above 65% of them disagreed that women marketers are treated with same respect and dignity as men and around 55% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers are treated with same respect and dignity as men. We can conclude that the most of the population disagreed that women marketers are treated with same respect and dignity as men.

Do You Think Women Marketers and Men Marketers are Paid Equally?

Table 8: Women Marketers and Men Marketers are Paid Equally

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	41	19.5
Disagree	58	27.6
Neither agree nor disagree	53	25.2
Agree	37	17.6
Strongly Agree	21	10.0
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 40% of them agree that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally, above 60% of them disagreed that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally and around 55% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally. One can conclude by saying that the most of the population

disagreed that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally.

Do You Think the Social Barriers for Women is Higher than Men?

Table 9: Social Barriers for Women is Higher than Men

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	22	10.5
Disagree	49	23.3
Neither agree nor disagree	39	18.6
Agree	54	25.7
Strongly Agree	46	21.9
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 65% of them agree that the social barriers for women is higher than men, above 50% of them disagreed that the social barriers for women is higher than men and around 40% neither agreed nor disagreed that the social barriers for women is higher than men. Thus, we can tell that the most of them agreed that the social barriers for women are higher that of men.

Do you Think the Ability of Women to Balance Their Work Life Will Affect the Perception of the Indians?

Table 10: Ability of Women to Balance Their Work Life Will Affect the Perception of the Indians

	Frequency	Percent
Strongly Disagree	31	14.8
Disagree	45	21.4
Neither agree nor disagree	45	21.4
Agree	58	27.6
Strongly Agree	31	14.8
Total	210	100.0

Inference: Around 70% of them agree that the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians, above 25% of them disagreed that the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians and around 40% neither agreed nor disagreed the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of Indians. Thus, we can tell that the most of them agreed that the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians.

CHI-Square Analysis

Table 11: Relationship between the Variables

Hypothesis	Significance Level	Sig Observed Value	Accepted/Rejected
There is no acceptance of women marketers across various dimensions (skillset, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance, competency, etc.,)	0.05%	0.040	H ₀ is rejected
There is no acceptance of women marketers across the skill sets	0.05%	0.040	H ₀ is rejected
There is no acceptance of women marketers across the social barriers	0.05%	0.041	H ₀ is rejected

Table 11: Contnd.,

There is no acceptance of women marketers across work-life balance.	0.05%	0.036	H ₀ is rejected
There is acceptance of women marketers across competencies.	0.05%	0.033	H ₀ is rejected

Table 11: Correlation Analysis of the Study Dimensions

		Sum of Skill Sets	Sum of Social Barriers	Sum of Competitiveness	Sum of Work Life	Sum of Acceptance
Skill sets	Pearson Correlation	1	.840**	.838**	.799**	.830**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.012
	N	210	210	210	210	210
Social Barriers	Pearson Correlation	.840**	1	.849**	.802**	.824**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.001
	N	210	210	210	210	210
Competitiveness	Pearson Correlation	.838**	.849**	1	.825**	.847**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.014
	N	210	210	210	210	210
Work Life Balance	Pearson Correlation	.799**	.802**	.825**	1	.802**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.024
	N	210	210	210	210	210
Acceptability	Pearson Correlation	.830**	.824**	.847**	.802**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.012	.001	.014	.024	
	N	210	210	210	210	210

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed) * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

FINDINGS AND SUGGESTIONS

Research Findings

- Out of the analysed respondents, around 60% of them agree that women marketers seek for challenging opportunities that test their skills and abilities and around 40% of them disagreed
- Out of the analysed respondents, around 60% of them agree that women marketers foresee the future trends that will influence the company's work and around 30% of them disagreed that women marketers foresee the future trends that will influence the company's work
- Around 50% of them agree that the women marketers develop a cooperative relationship among their co-workers and around 30% of them disagreed that the women marketers develop cooperative relationship among their co-workers
- Around 60% of them agree that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make. around 25% of them disagreed that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make and around 50% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers follow the promises and commitments they make.
- Around 60% of them agree that women marketers help people to progress in their job by learning new skills and around 20% of them disagreed that women marketers help people to progress in their job by learning new skills and around 40% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers help people grow in their jobs by learning new

skills

- Around 40% of them agree that women marketers are treated with respect and dignity as men, above 65% of them disagreed that women marketers are treated with the same respect and dignity as men and around 55% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers are treated with respect and dignity as men
- According to the people of Bangalore, around 40% of them agree that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally, above 60% of them disagreed that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally and around 55% neither agreed nor disagreed that women marketers and men marketers are paid equally
- Around 70% of them agree that the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians, above 25% of them disagreed that the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians and around 40% neither agreed nor disagreed the ability of women to balance their work life will affect the perception of the Indians

Overall Findings And Suggestions

- Acceptance of women marketers by the people is highly influenced by various dimensions such as a skillset, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance, competencies etc.
- The correlation of skillset factors with all the four analysed dimensions (i.e. social barriers, competitiveness, work-life balance, acceptance) are found to be positive and significant (at 1% level) indicating that the skillset of the women marketers will aid in acceptance
- Observing the correlation values in the table, shows that the relationship between skillset, competitiveness, work-life balance, social-cultural barriers and acceptance is very high indicating that the social barriers of the women marketers will aid in acceptance
- As per the table, it indicates that the social barriers, work-life balance of the women marketers will aid in acceptance as null hypothesis is rejected
- In Anova, the p value $0.000 < \text{significance value of } 0.05$ and thus we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternate hypothesis which in this case is the skillset, social-cultural barriers, competitiveness, work life balance and acceptance are dependent on each other
- Each dimension's co-relational values impact has been analysed against the acceptance and we arrive at competitiveness stands on the top at 0.830 followed by skillset at 0.830, social-cultural barriers at 0.824 and finally with the work life balance at 0.802
- The competitiveness is highly dependent on how the public acceptance on women marketers; we can suggest the organizations can hire more women marketers as it is proved that their skillsets, competitiveness, work life balance and social-cultural barriers are equal with men.
- While formulating an efficient business plan, the companies should design policies and frameworks that could support and empower women to take up greater positions.

- Women Empowerment strategies need to be aligned with the company's requirement and women's abilities and potentialities.
- Companies should encourage constant feedback systems about the work environment and focus on creating a better place to work
- Organizations should encourage workshops, seminars and training to widen the horizon of men and women employees and groom them to assume higher positions in the organisations.

CONCLUSIONS

As the above research is about the perception of Indians on women marketers, we can conclude by saying that there is a dependency on the skillset a woman marketing personnel possess and the acceptance of her in the corporate world. There is a relationship between how you perceive women in the field of marketing and their skillset and social-cultural barriers they face, the competitiveness in the market for and against the women marketing personnel and the ability of women to balance their work and personal life.

Organizations should encourage their employees to prosper and excel based on their skillset but not on gender basis. All the employees should get equal opportunities to showcase their talent. To make the work environment better, seminars and different events need to be conducted to eliminate the line drawn in the past between male and female working capabilities.

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WOMEN MARKETERS: INCLUSIVENESS AND OPPORTUNITIES FOR CAREER GROWTH AND ADVANCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

Indian women span generations and today they play equal participants in every field. Breaking the chains of restraint, women have become ever-motivated and inspired and are riding on the wave of success. The discourses on women's empowerment have increased in general and become more widespread. Women have revolutionised the existing corporate ecosystem. This paper focuses on the perceptions of the Indians on women marketers and their capabilities and potentialities like skill set, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance and competency. The primary objective of the paper is to understand the association of various dimensions pertaining to the acceptance of women marketers in their career growth and build a relationship between the acceptance of women marketers across dimensions of skill set, socio-cultural barriers, work-life balance and competency. Statistical tool used is SPSS 21 and Chi-Square, Correlation test and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Test (KMO) was conducted to test the hypothesis. The study findings revealed that there is an association between the dimensions of acceptance and the career opportunities provided to the women marketers.

Keywords: Women Empowerment, Marketing Roles, skill Sets, Competency & Work Life

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INTRODUCTION

Gender refers to the socially constructed roles, behaviours, activities and attributes that a given society considers appropriate for men and women (WHO report, 2012).

With a decline in their status from the ancient to medieval times, to the promotion of equal rights by many reformers, the history of women in India has been eventful (Jayapalan 2001). Women in India now participate fully in areas such as education, sports, politics, media, art and culture, service sectors, science and technology, etc. (NRCW, 2006).

Earlier, men were assumed to be more capable and successful than women in all the sectors. Today we are witnessing a trend of a growing brigade of women marketing officers. Women managers and leaders are in huge demand in marketing, media and advertising departments, giving their ability to multitask and their understanding of the core consumers. When dealing with women as a consumer, most marketers think it is wise to have women leaders to frame the product strategies. We see this new trend plays out and as an indication of robust participation of women in the marketing area and the corporate world.